

Storm-surge simulations: a quantitative comparison of some open-source shallow-water solvers

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Abstract

This contribution promotes a unified and objective assessment of the simulation skills for coastal flooding using available exact benchmarks for wind-driven flows proposed by Sobey (2002). It will present the quantitative comparison between the well-known shallow-water solvers ADCIRC, DELFT3D and TELEMAC against exact unsteady solutions under steady and unsteady wind forcing. It emphasizes the scope and significance of accurate simulations in view of the increased adoption of risk-based policies for coastal management.

Wind-driven shallow-flow processes: from physics to society The shallowness of basins amplifies the effects of the atmospheric forcing on the water surface, leaving the coastline exposed to flows with high potential and kinetic energy. Storm surges and meteo-tsunamis are examples of processes where this mechanics is at play.

Undesirably, flooding and consequent loss of property and life may result. Great societal concerns are justified owing to a growing global population being concentrated in coastal areas, to weather anomalies and events expected to increase after climate change and to flood-proneness being aggravated by human-induced land subsidence.

Shallow-flow simulations and decision-making In this context, computer simulations of shallow flows contribute key quantitative information to decisions with huge geographical coverage, future projection and societal relevance. For example, hindcasts and forecasts of severe events explain the dynamics of surges; help set the levels of alertness, preparedness and response; support long-term planning of preventative and mitigating measures.

Importantly, decisions concerning the vulnerability of coastal areas are often based on a risk-based approach. The local level of protection against flooding is gauged against both the probability of an impacting event (hazard) and the monetized appraisal of the expected loss of property and life consequent on the impact (damage). Regarded as the product of hazard and damage, risk is a commonly adopted metric for decisions and interventions.

Risk-based approach and flow solvers Since computer simulations define both the exposure to hazards (the trespassing of the damage threshold) and the magnitude of the ensuing impacts, part of the vulnerability of any flood-prone area can be attributed to the performance of the flow solver producing those simulations.

Furthermore, since any flow solver delivers its own approximation of the statements of mass and momentum conservation (in view of the chosen mathematical formulation, solving algorithms and software coding), recognizable and quantifiable simulation errors ought not to bias the assessment of exposure and vulnerability, hence of risk.

Flow solvers and quantitative error assessment In general, the test suites used for the quality assurance of different solvers differ as well. However, since the shallow-water solvers ADCIRC, DELFT3D and TELEMAC are open-source software nowadays, independent cross-comparison is eventually feasible.

In particular, Sobey's analytical solutions address the unsteady wind-driven flow within simplified basins. In spite of the necessary linearisation, the equations retain a great deal of the mechanical complexity at play also when non-linearities (advection, quadratic friction) are considered. Notably, the wind forcing also schematises rapidly varying situations mimicking squall lines.

As a result, the propagation of the analytical surge within the schematised basins features rapid changes in sign and in rates of change in both the water level and depth-averaged velocity. Therefore, this complexity is well-suited to test the backbone of the numerical schemes and of the solving algorithms in a flow solver, the simplifications notwithstanding.

The viability of this exercise has been proven by Lipari (2015) for the case of the D-FLOW FM flow solver.

References

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